

Awareness and Attitude Toward Sex Education and Social Development of Social Studies Students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the awareness and attitude towards sex education and social development of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State. The research was carried out among junior secondary school students in Delta State. The design for the study was a correlation research design. The population for the study were 25,602 upper students in the 2024/2025 academic session. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select five hundred and twelve (512) students as the sample for the study. The instrument for the study was a 36-item questionnaire designed by the researcher. The validity was established using expert judgment. A test-retest was used to establish the reliability. The instrument had a coefficient reliability index value of 0.80. Data generated were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while the hypotheses were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 significance level. The findings show that the level of awareness and attitude affects sex education and social development. It was recommended that both parents and teachers should encourage the teaching of sex education at home and in schools right from childhood to improve the level of awareness of social studies students. Social studies students should be enlightened to have a positive attitude towards learning sex education to improve their social development and avoid harmful sexual practices which can harm or destroy their entire lives.

INTRODUCTION

Education shapes human being's life in positive ways. Education is a human right that should be bestowed on human beings exclusively because there should be a positive relationship between sex education and social development, as it was propounded before by many theorists and researchers who argued that exploring and comprehending the effects of family and community on sexuality, on the other hand, is a challenging aspect of sex education (Sabejeje & Bello, 2021). The establishment of education is key, as well as an index of social development above and beyond understanding the implication of unawareness of sex education among students (Obro & Enayemo, 2022). Usually, education draws its

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content from social demography, human ecology, and family life. The fact is that the majority of the students might not know the effect of sex education, which is unwanted pregnancy, regularly due to inadequate information about sexual awareness. In most cases, sexual abuse can lead to early pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases.

UNESCO (2009) posited that the primary goal of sex education is to provide students and young adults with the abilities, cognition and strategies to make the right choices about sexuality and how to prevent student sexual abuse. Sex education will not only help the individual to learn about sexual abuse but also help children to learn about childhood pregnancy, HIV and AIDs, sexually transmitted diseases and infections. Students also need to know about the risks, causes and signs of sexual abuse for them to recognise the problem of sexual intentions, even before they occur, so that they can prevent it, protect themselves and get support (Venkat & Navya, 2013).

Students' awareness of sex education may constitute the effectiveness of the social development of students across the country. Awareness is knowing information concerning a specific person or object that benefits humanity within the environment. Awareness is regarded as a social activity that allows us to get the help of those around us who can influence (positively or negatively) our awareness and lead to greater shared awareness. Awareness is a comprehension of the activities of other people, which provides content and avenues for your activity. In research networks, awareness encompasses a larger significance relating to trendiness, dissemination of research findings within a particular domain, alterations in the structure and functioning of a network, and individual factors.

An attitude can be seen as a feeling people have towards something meaningful within a specific period (Wehr-Flowers, 2016). Attitude may be included because a teacher's attitude toward the subject matter influences what is taught, how it is taught, and who is expected to be learned. An attitude is an organised and interconnected set of ideas, emotions, and behavioural inclinations about socially significant

items, groups, events, or symbols (Hogg & Vaughan, 2005). Attitude is a psychological inclination manifested through assessing a specific entity with varying levels of satisfaction or discontent (Eagly & Chaiken, 2007). The extent of their stability and end would be expected to fall on a continuum and is determined by factors such as cognitive structure.

Sex education can be classified as a way of teaching children moral values that are attached to male and female future life. The extent of sex education can be as a way of teaching students the implications of sexual intercourse at the early stage of teenage. Sex education is fundamentally fairly an extensive one used to describe teaching relating to human sexual anatomy, reproduction, intercourse and other components connected to human sexual behaviour. It is a mechanism that stands for the protection, enhancement, and development of the human person and family based on putative ethical values and ideas (Wood & Leandre, 2015).

An overarching definition of social development would be the progression of a student's interests from less demanding to more demanding in areas such as activity, quality, educational output, complexity, understanding, creativity, agency, competence, pleasure, and achievement. Olubayo (2012) says, "By development, I mean the upward movement of the whole social system." This is the only challenge that makes sense for students. Besides the so-called "human factors," this social system includes all the "non-human factors," such as the types of things that different groups of people buy and how they get them; the levels and types of schools and hospitals; the way power is distributed in society; and the differences in economic, social, and political status; and finally, the institutions and attitudes that people have. These exogenous factors cause policy measures to be taken to change some or all of the "endogenous factors."

Social development tries to reduce differences and calls for a society where everyone has the same amount of money and wealth, following the concept of equity. Achieving the well-being of the population and making development a holistic endeavour for all constitute the essence of social development.

However, it must be known that under the garb of modernisation and development motive, human ideals have also been promoted to a broader extent, which social studies students need to be aware of. This poses a challenge to the distinctiveness of the non-western developing societies. Aminat (2019) said there is a need to engage with the non-western conceptions of social development and give a broader scope to the local cultural conditions, making development a truly inclusive process in as much there is a transformation of adequate awareness and attitude towards sex education during teaching learning in upper basic school.

Attainment of social development embraces all aspects of social behaviour, such as the establishment of law and order over sexual abuse, resourcefulness in dealings with human attitude, honesty, sophistication, broad-mindedness, greater use of science and technology and overall positive national outlook (Ugwuja, 2018). With the recent movement towards globalisation where national boundaries matter less, social development has come to denote developmental activities that flow freely across national borders, inform of diffusion and innovations of goods and services, knowledge, skills, ideas, inventions, practices, etc., mostly from area of higher concentration to lower concentration (developing to developed culture) making the world a global community.

The religious beliefs held by parents can influence their methods of addressing sex education with their children. Parents with conservative religious beliefs may be less inclined to foster open discussions regarding sexual matters with their children (Miller & Olson, 2015). Parental beliefs have traditionally influenced family practices, often leading to resistance against the inclusion of sex education for children. This opposition may also impact the social development of students across various courses. Religious teachings underscore the significant contributions of both men and women in family life. According to Volling, Mahoney, and Rauer (2009), parents who practise a religion that influences their beliefs and actions may find it difficult to stress the value of family ties and dedication to others that motivates them to be actively involved in their children's lives. Parents might use religious belief to reduce social

development by failing to educate their children on sex education at an early stage due to family heritage (Odofin, Obro & Oletu, 2024).

The social development of Social Studies students depends on their attitude among their age group. Parents often say they don't want to discuss sexuality with their teens because they are afraid that in-depth discussion will appear as a license to take pleasure in sexual behaviour. A good awareness and attitude of Social Studies students toward sex education will enable students to have an adequate idea of how to utilise the knowledge acquired from teaching and learning Social Studies to build social development. The relevance of sex education as a means of developing healthy attitudes can be proved on various accounts. Many educationists agree that school is the best place to administer formal sex education to children who undergoing development or growth in subsequent time. Sex education may serve as a comprehensive program that addresses various facets of human development to provide individuals with essential information to protect themselves and make informed decisions (Leung, 2019). Therefore, the study investigates awareness and attitudes toward sex education and social development of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

- i. To examine the relationship between Social Studies student's awareness of sex education and their social development.
- ii. To determine the relationship between Social Studies student's attitudes toward sex education and their social development.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between the awareness level of social studies students on sex education and social development in Delta State?
2. What is the attitude of Social Studies students on sex education and social development in Delta State?

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Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between social studies students' awareness level and sex education/social development.
2. There is no significant relationship between the attitude of Social Studies students and sex education/social development.

METHODS

The design for this study is a Correlation research design as it deals with the relationship between variables. Aboyi (2017) opined that correlation research design investigates the relationship between variables without the research controlling or manipulating them. The population for the study comprised 25,602 upper-basic eight students from three senatorial districts in Delta State. This study's sample comprised five hundred and twelve (512) upper-basic school students. The instrument used for the data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument is titled Social Studies Students Awareness and Attitude Toward Sex Education and Social Development Questionnaire (SSSAATSESDQ). It consists of two parts. Part one contained the personal bio-data of the respondents, while part two consisted of thirty-six (36) items. The research questions were answered with the use of mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at a 0.05 significance level. The decision rule was applied to the research questions. Items with mean scores of 2.50 and above were accepted, while Items with mean scores below 2.50 were rejected.

RESULTS

RQ 1: What is the relationship between the awareness level of social studies students on sex education and social development in Delta State?

Table 2: Level of awareness of social studies students on sex education and social development in Delta State

S/N	ITEMS	SA		A		D		SD		TOTAL		\bar{x}	STD	DECISION
		FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS			
1	My awareness level helps me to take precautions against sexual harassment	201	804	115	345	121	242	75	75	512	1466	2.86	1.10	Accept
2	My awareness level of sex education is high	157	628	120	360	115	230	120	120	512	1338	2.61	1.15	Accept
3	My awareness level helps to prevent me from sexual relationship	145	580	192	576	98	196	77	77	512	1429	2.79	1.02	Accept
4	My awareness level enables me to know the stages of sexual development	120	480	120	360	115	230	157	157	512	1227	2.40	1.15	Reject
5	My sexual prevention is high due to the level of awareness	150	600	132	396	138	276	92	92	512	1364	2.66	1.08	Accept
6	My level of awareness encourages me to study sex education	166	664	129	387	108	216	109	109	512	1376	2.69	1.14	Accept
Mean Grand Total													16.01	
Aggregate Mean													2.67	Accept

Benchmark = 2.50

Table 1 analysis revealed that Item I has a mean of 2.80, indicating that awareness level of sex education and social development will help to take precautions against sexual harassment of the social studies students in Delta State. Item II has a mean of 2.61, above the benchmark of 2.50, indicating that the awareness level of social studies students in Delta State is high. Item III has a mean of 2.79; therefore, we accept that the social students' awareness level will contribute to their sexual relationship. Item IV has a mean of 2.40; thus, Item IV is rejected; we reject that awareness level will not help the social studies students to know all the stages of sexual development. Item V has a mean of 2.66, which is above 2.50; therefore, sexual prevention of the social studies students results from high awareness. Item VI mean of 2.66 is also above 2.50; hence, we accept that a level of awareness will encourage social studies students to study sex education. The aggregate mean of 2.67 is accepted since it is above 2.50. Therefore, the awareness level of the social studies students in Delta State is related to their sex education.

RQ2: What is the attitude of Social Studies students on sex education and social development in Delta State?

Table 2: Attitude of Social Studies students on sex education in Delta State

S/N	ITEMS	SA		A		D		SD		TOTAL		\bar{X}	STD	Decision
		FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS	FC	WS			
1	My sexual feelings were reduced because of my attitude.	209	836	158	474	65	130	80	80	512	1520	2.96	1.08	Accept
2	My attitude prevents me from having knowledge of sex education.	180	720	195	585	84	168	53	53	512	1553	2.98	0.97	Accept
3	My attitude prevents me from sexual harassment	175	700	182	546	83	166	72	72	512	1484	2.90	1.03	Accept
4	My sexual behaviour changes due to my attitude	156	624	182	546	84	168	90	78	512	1416	2.79	1.06	Accept
5	My attitude toward sex education prevents me from sexual transmission disease, STD	145	580	133	399	125	250	109	109	512	1338	2.61	1.11	Accept
6	My attitude discourages me having an awareness of sex education	132	528	115	345	79	158	186	186	512	1217	2.38	1.22	Reject
Mean Grand Total												16.62		
Aggregate Mean												2.77		

Benchmark = 2.50

Table 3 analysis shows that Item I has a mean of 2.96; hence, we accept that attitude will help to reduce sexual feelings. Item II of Table 3 has a mean of 2.98; hence, we accept that attitude affects the knowledge of sex education of social studies students. The Mean of Item III is 2.90; we therefore accept that the attitude of social studies students will prevent sexual harassment. Item IV has a mean of 2.79. Hence, we accept that attitude will bring about changes in sexual behaviour. Item V had 2.61 as the mean; we equally accept that attitude towards sex education will prevent sexually transmitted diseases. Item VI has a mean of 2.38. Therefore, we reject that attitude does not discourage social studies students' awareness of sex education. The aggregate mean of 2.77 is above the benchmark of 2.50. Therefore, the attitude of the Delta State social studies students is related to their sex education.

Hypotheses Testing

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Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social studies students’ awareness level and sex education/social development.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between the level of awareness of social studies students and sex education/social development.

		Awareness Level	Sex Education/Social Development
Awareness Level	Pearson Correlation	1	0.009
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.840
	N	512	512
Sex Education/Social Development	Pearson Correlation	0.009	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.840	
	N	512	512

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 analysis revealed that a p-value of 0.840 is significant since 0.840 is greater than 0.05. However, the r-value of $0.009 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Awareness level has an effect or is related to sex education/social development.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the attitude of Social Studies students and sex education/social development.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between the attitude of Social Studies students and sex education/social development.

		Attitude	Sex education/Social development.
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	0.048
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.278
	N	512	512
Sex education/Social development.	Pearson Correlation	0.048	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.278	
	N	512	512

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Pearson Product Moment correlational statistical analysis of Table 9 revealed that a p-value of 0.278 is less than 0.05, an r-value of $0.048 < 0.05$; hence, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. In other words, a significant relationship exists between social studies attitude and sex education/social development.

DISCUSSION

The hypothesis revealed that awareness level is directly proportional to sex education/social development. This implies that a high level of awareness will improve sex education and social development, while a low level of awareness will negatively affect sex education/social development. This study corroborates with Fentahun, Assefu, Alemseged and Aniba (2012) and Madkour, Xie & Harville (2013) that a high level of awareness will have a positive impact negatively. Obro (2020), in his study of a study of the level of awareness and attitude of upper basic Social Studies students towards sex education equally found that there is no significant difference in Social Studies student's level of awareness of sex education; in other words, there is a relationship in the level of awareness of Social Studies students on sex education and social development. Ademuyiwa, Ayamolowo, Oshinyemi and Oyeku (2023) pointed out in their study that a high level of sex education awareness will significantly enhance the relationship between students' knowledge and attitude towards sex education and social development. This study has, therefore, revealed the need for awareness and effective sex education among secondary school students. It can, thus, be concluded that teachers and parents should create a view to improve the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education as it will bring overall social development that will positively affect the larger society.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that the attitude of the social study student is related to sex education and social development. In-depth analysis shown that this attitude towards sex education will help to prevent sexually transmitted diseases, improve sexual behaviour and avoid sexual harassment. This study aligned with Akpania (2013) and Anulika (2019); both studies agreed that a good attitude towards sex education and social development will help overcome sexual embarrassment and improve sexual health. This finding has, therefore, stressed the need to teach sex education from early childhood to adulthood to have an enhanced society where social development is improved right from childhood to adulthood. This study has encouraged both parents at home and teachers in school to help build children's

attitudes towards a sound sex education that will improve society. This can be achieved through the teaching of children by parents on the importance of sex education and the implication of not having knowledge of sex education that will negatively affect the attitude of children as it relates to sex education. School authorities should include sex education in the school curriculum right from primary school level to secondary school level to help build children's positive attitude towards sex education that will bring about improved social development in our society.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings, it established that the level of awareness of sex education is associated with social development. It also established that attitude plays a key role in sex education and social development. A positive attitude will enhance sex education and improve social development. The study affirms the need to improve awareness and attitude towards improving sex education and social development. The level of sex education awareness has the same implication for male and female social studies students in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Both parents and teachers should encourage the teaching of sex education at home and in schools right from childhood to improve the level of awareness of social studies students.
2. Social Studies students should be enlightened to have a positive attitude towards learning sex education to improve their social development and avoid harmful sexual practices which can harm or destroy their entire lives.

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